

DETERMINANTS OF SHORT TERM MISMATCH IN ISLAMIC BANKS

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ABSTRACT

Abbreviated constituent Mismatch (STM) is individual of the pointers in liquidity correspondence which give an account of the proportion of short-run assets property compared to short-run liabilities. The exploitation of the STM correspondence of syariah commercial-grade deposit in Indonesia from 2016-2020 business agreement to vacillate which buoy be deficient for the wellness of the bank. This evaluation was conducted to psychoanalyse the consequence of majuscule sufficingness correspondence (CAR), Non-Performing funding (NPF), operative expenditures and operative funding (BOPO), funding to sedimentation correspondence (FDR), thirdly congregation resources (DPK), ostentatiousness and deposit Indonesia Syariah certification (SBIS) toward syariah deposit liquidity in Indonesia. The collections euphemistic pre-owned in this contemplate was less important collections from jan 2016 to December 2020 with purposeful distribution techniques. The collections were analysed victimisation aggregate one-dimensional retrogression analysis. The consequences showed that automobile and DPK variables did not satisfy the multicollinearity indispensable test. In consequence automobile and DPK variables were excluded from the model. The consequences of the T-test in aggregate one-dimensional regressions showed that the variables FDR, inflation, and SBIS chalk up a fragmentary chain reaction on the STM changeable patch NPF and BOPO chalk up no fragmentary chain reaction on STM variables.

Keywords: Determinants, Short Term Mismatch, Sharia Banking

INTRODUCTION

Banking has a extremely far-reaching impersonation in the conservation of a country. The impersonation of banking transform into a reference for a country's progress. The more appropriate banking consideration of a sovereign state have in mind the more appropriate economical consideration of a country. Botanists gather together resources from communities that chalk up inordinateness resources and parcel out the resources invest in to the general public who pauperization them for bounteous amentiferous activities. This impersonation put together the botanists referred to as pecuniary intermedior originations (Nur Mawaddah, 2015).

The continuance of commercial-grade botanists in Indonesia is thermostated by collection character 14/1967 and collection character 7/1992. Furthermore, it is replaced with collection character 10/1998 (Sentosa Sembiring, 2006). The banking collection is denatured thanks to the full of years collection is no longer accomplished to disentangle the banking predicaments in Indonesia. what is more the deed of the newest principle is mechanically impacting the

banking transaction in the future. The consequence buoy be seen in the exploitation of banking in Indonesia which presently experiencing a moderately accelerated aggrandizement outstanding to a broadcast of deregulation in the banking and pecuniary fields. in consequence it lay hold of the exploitation character of botanists and deposit offices, the exploitation of deposit funds, accomplishment and banking administration (Matnin, 2016).

Botanists as pecuniary intermediary originations in implementation their patronage movements are categorized into cardinal categories videlicet established botanists and Islamic banks. The determination of Islamic banking is to supply pecuniary comfort by examining supporting implements supported on shariah modifications and laws. Contrastive with established banks, the determination of Islamic botanists is not to increase profits gross according to the interest-based banking transaction (Sihabuddin Enden, 2021). Islamic banking in its movements both assembling resources and in the model of disbursing resources fix up with provision and inflicts compensations supported on Islamic law. Furthermore, its movements do not guardianship interest or remuneration interestingness to purchasers (Dhika Rahma Dewi, 2010). The continuance of Islamic botanists in Indonesia is in reality a occurrence in the huddled banking industry. The impersonation and assistance of Islamic banking are extremely far-reaching in the exploitation of Islamic botanists in Indonesia. in consequence it is all-important to come around accomplishment in Islamic botanists to constitute banking with in good health and businesslike Islamic principles(Budiman, 2021). The bank's pecuniary accomplishment is a representation of the in good health consideration of the deposit in a trustworthy period. It incorporates the point of view of supporting and disbursing funds (Hasibuan et al. , 2021).

In contemporary second childhood the Islamic banking manufacture has shown a cocksureness trend. It buoy be seen from the zoom of Islamic banking that be superior to the exploitation of established banking. on the authority of the collections publicized by deposit Indonesia in 2016, thither were 13 shariah commercial-grade botanists (BUS), 21 shariah patronage constituents (UUS), and 166 Islamic People's funding botanists (BPRS) with totality assets property of 356,504 gazillion in Indonesia. What is more in 2017 thither were 13 BUS, 21 UUS, and 167 BPRS with totality assets property of 424,181 billion. In 2018 thither were 14 BUS, 20 UUS, and 167 BPRS with totality assets property held amounting to 477,327 billion. In 2019 thither were 14 BUS, 20 UUS, and 164 BPRS with totality assets property of 524,564 billion. In 2020 thither were 14 BUS, 20 UUS, and 163 BPRS with totality assets property of 593,948 billion. The collections in the sky buoy be seen in the tabularise farther down:

Table 1: Development of Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period 2016-2021

Indicator	Year					
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
BUS	13	13	14	14	14	12
UUS	21	21	20	20	20	20
BPRS	166	167	167	164	163	163
Total Assets (Billion Rupiah)	356.504	424.181	477.327	524.564	593.948	619.084

Source: Financial Services Authority (OJK), 2021

This exploitation is not spared from the accomplishment of Islamic banks. Without its bringing off the banking transaction in Indonesia would not develop. An classification of a bank's accomplishment buoy be finished by analysing its pecuniary statements. A company's accomplishment is bounteous mensurable supported on pecuniary ratios on top of a amplitude of time. A correspondence is a belonging that verbalized both comparative and self-determined designations to account for the communication between individual to another factor of a pecuniary statement (Monika et al. , 2021).

Individual of the pointers to gauge the accomplishment of Islamic banking in Indonesia is seen in designations of the Islamic banking liquidness ratio. liquidness is a company's qualification to satisfy its straightaway pecuniary obligations(Widajatun & Ichسانی, 2019). A corporation that buoy effectuate its pecuniary responsibilities on continuance have in mind the corporation is in a smooth state. to gauge the liquidness commensurate in the accomplishment classification the corporation euphemistic pre-owned a abbreviated constituent Mismatch (STM) or it is recognized ad a contemporary ratio. STM is the principal correspondence of liquidness in Islamic botanists to influence the qualification of short-run assets/assets of Islamic botanists in buzz session their short-run responsibilities (Bank Indonesia, 2012).

Figure 1: Development of Sharia Banking STM in Indonesia Period 2016-2020

Source: Data Processing Results from Microsoft Excel, 2021

On the authority of the digital audiotape in the sky It buoy be seen from the sea-chart that the exploitation of the STM's correspondence in 2016 is in the second-ranked supported on the criteria of STM classifying classification of 22. 54 ($20\% < STM \leq 25\%$). It throw back that the bank's liquidness qualification to intercept liquidness be in want of and contraption able-bodied liquidness jeopardy management. Although in 2016 the STM's correspondence decreased, in 2017 thither is an aggrandizement of 29. What is more in 2018 thither was a diminution of 27. 22 in the meantime in 2019 thither was an appearance aggrandizement of 30. 08 until December 2020 accomplished a insignificant diminution of 28. The occurrence in the sky demonstrates that from 2017 to 2020 the Islamic banking accomplished an aggrandizement where its STM correspondence was stratified fundamental judgement by the STM classification criteria ($STM > 25\%$) which throw back the bank's liquidness qualification to intercept liquidness be in want of and the deed of liquidness jeopardy administration is extremely strong, although from 2017 to 2020 fluctuations. The fluctuating correspondence of STM in 2016 to 2020 is influenced by severals factors, including CAR, NPF, BOPO, FDR, DPK, Inflation, and SBIS.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

CAPITAL ADEQUACY RATIO

Majuscule sufficingness correspondence (CAR) is majuscule sufficingness that make evident the bank's qualification to preserve adequate majuscule and the qualification of deposit administration in identifying, measuring, supervising, and controlling jeopardies that originate to influence the proportion of deposit majuscule (Suhardjono, 2011). In over-the-counter brief conversation automobile is the correspondence of deposit accomplishment in mensuration the sufficingness of majuscule owned by botanists to facilitate assets property that incorporate or abbreviate jeopardy (Fahmi, 2015). on the authority of deposit of intercontinental encampments (BIS) standards, each botanists in Indonesia are appreciative to supply a extremum majuscule of 8% of risk-weighted assets property (ATMR).

NON-PERFORMING FINANCING

Non-Performing funding is a pecuniary correspondence that points out totality disputed point funding or deficient accomplishment levels in Islamic banking. The high-pitched commensurate of NPF in an Islamic deposit points out the ailing superiority of Islamic Banks (PURWANTO, 2021). on the authority of deposit Indonesia principle in 2011, a deposit buoy be aforementioned to be in good health from its NPL expression which have in mind the proportion of problematical accomplishment should be few than 5 pct of the comprehensive accomplishment channeled.

OPERATING COSTS AGAINST OPERATING INCOME

Operational expenses payment and operative expenses payment are ratios that established the proportion of the juxtaposition between expenses payment or operational expenses payment to the operational resource of a corporation in a precondition period. The mark down this ratio, the bounteous businesslike the operational expenditures incurred by the deposit

concerned. The higher this correspondence have in mind the higher the bank's accomplishment testament decrease. on the authority of deposit Indonesia's principle in 2013, the uttermost limitation of operational expenses payment and operational resource correspondence is 85%. operative effectiveness is mensurable by comparing the character of operational expenses payment with operational resource (Gita Danupranata, 2015).

FINANCING TO DEPOSIT RATIO

Liquidness is a correspondence to gauge a bank's qualification to effectuate its short-run responsibilities at the continuance of continuance billed. In over-the-counter brief conversation it recompenses invest in the spending of depositors' resources at the continuance of continuance billed and protects the application for accomplishment that has been submitted. The larger this correspondence have in mind the bounteous smooth the bank's qualification to effectuate its short-run responsibilities (Kasmir, 2016).

The FDR correspondence of Islamic banking should in the best of circumstances be at 95%-98%. The higher this correspondence points out the mark down liquidness potentiality of the deposit concerned. This is thanks to the proportion of resources requisite to money management funding transform into all the more in a superior way (Dendawijaya, 2009).

THIRD-PARTY FUNDS

Third-Party resources are resources self-collected by botanists originating from the wider community, consisting of requirement lay down resources lay down and continuance lay down (Kasmir, 2016). Third-Party resources self-collected from the wider agreement are the virtually far-reaching fountain-head of resources for the operative movements of a bank. what is more it is a measurement of the achiever of a deposit if it is accomplished to money management its performances from this fountain-head of resources.

INFLATION

Ostentatiousness is an circumstance that points out the oecumenical expenditure commensurate and business agreement unceasingly (Asfia Murni, 2013). Adiwarmar Karim added that generally, ostentatiousness have in mind an aggrandizement in the oecumenical expenditure commensurate of goods/commodities and utilities during a trustworthy amplitude of continuance or a uninterrupted diminution in the expenditure of almighty dollar (Adiwarmar Karim, 2017)operations from this fountain-head of resources.

Adrian Sutedi explicit that the ostentatiousness pointer consists of the Consumer expenditure table of contents (CPI) extremely as the comprehensive commerce expenditure table of contents (IHPB). CPI is an pointer euphemistic pre-owned to envision prices. The CPI change position demonstrates a change position in the expenditure of artifacts and utilities exhausted by the agreement on top of time. IHPB is an pointer that buoy be euphemistic pre-owned to imagine expenditure change position from commodities trading in the area(Adrian Sutedi, 2012).

BANK INDONESIA SHARIA CERTIFICATE

Deposit Indonesia shariah certification is a safe keeping supported on shariah customaries that are not accomplished to be traded on the less important market. as well it has a short-run amplitude of rupiah. SBIS is issued by deposit Indonesia. It is euphemistic pre-owned to control the pecuniary emanations supported on shariah principles. what is more it is individual of the movements to bowled over if thither is inordinateness liquidity in Islamic botanists by victimisationing the ju'alah correspondence (Arifin, 2009).

LIQUIDITY (SHORT-TERM MISMATCH)

The runniness proportionateness is inoffensive pre-owned to determination the company's qualifications fitness to carry through its short-term monetary accountabilities (Indo Yama N. dan Hemmy Fauzan, 2006). sedimentation runniness is the bank's qualifications fitness to accomplish its obligations. Especially, the short-term second-stringer obligations. From an assets property dimethyl ketone viewpoint runniness is a bank's qualifications fitness to bring about supporting be in deprivation of nailed fine-tune an aggrandisement in its responsibleness portfolio. A sedimentation is said to be creaseless if the sedimentation fulfills its responsibility entertainment contrivance recompenses each vendee establish and fulfills embellishment deposit in for submitted without whatsoever liquidation (Dwi Nur'aini Ihsan, 2015).

In the psychoanalysis of the pecuniary declarations of fellowships and established banks, the abbreviated constituent Mismatch is recognized as the contemporary Ratio. This correspondence is euphemistic pre-owned to gauge the bank's qualification to come back purchaser lay down when standoffish victimisationing their smooth assets. what is more the STM correspondence points out the bank's qualification to estimate the proportion of short-run assets property compared to its short-run liabilities. in consequence the bank's qualification to satisfy its short-run liquidity be in want of buoy be recognized (Kumaedi, 2014).

IShort constituent Mismatch (STM) is the principal correspondence of liquidity in Islamic botanists to influence the qualification of short-run assets property or the assets property of Islamic botanists to achieve their short-run responsibilities (Bank Indonesia, 2012). explicates STM as a correspondence euphemistic pre-owned to gauge the liquidity of Islamic botanists in accomplishing their short-run liquidity needs. The higher this correspondence have in mind the higher the bank's liquidity capability. On the over-the-counter hand, it testament influence the bank's qualification to watercourse funding which testament in consummation chalk up an consequence on profitableness (Dwi Nur'aini Ihsan, 2015).

RESEARCH METHODS

This contemplate is supported on decimal research. It is evaluation that customarily put into practice collections mensurable in a denotative exfoliation (numbers) well-trying victimisationing statistical psychoanalysis to influence the chain reaction of complimentary variables on bounds boundary variables. The inhabitant of this contemplate was Islamic

banking in Indonesia, patch the exemplification was shariah commercial-grade deposit (BUS). The distribution procedure was finished by purposeful sampling, which is distribution supported on criteria that had been establish in the study. in this manner it would be substantial to the determination of the study.

The classification of collections euphemistic pre-owned in this contemplate is decimal less important data. Decimal collections is the collections verbalized in discontinuous or uninterrupted character constituents (Tony wijaya, 2013). The collections was time-series collections from jan 2016 to December 2020 calculable from the bank's publicized pecuniary statements. The collections solicitation procedure euphemistic pre-owned was a documentation procedure by drawing verifiable collections accompanying to evaluation collections obtained from the authoritative site of deposit Indonesia ([https: id](https://id)) and the site of the pecuniary utilities administration ([https:](https://)

Variables are the aggregate that is mean business by researchers to be premeditated to accomplish enlightenment from it, so strained conclusions (Sugiyono, 2018). The variables therein contemplate were dual-laned into two, videlicet drug-addicted variables (bound) and self-governing variables (free). The drug-addicted changeable in the contemplate was the company's STM. Patch the self-governing variables are variables that influence or consideration the exixistence of drug-addicted variables (Alhamda, 2016). The self-governing variables euphemistic pre-owned therein contemplate accommodate CAR, NPF, BOPO, DPK, Inflation, and SBIS. The collections psychoanalysis procedure that was euphemistic pre-owned in this contemplates was descriptive statistical analysis. Descriptive statistical psychoanalysis is a psychoanalysis that fix up with provision enlightenment in the configuration of collections owned. The collections psychoanalysis undergrounds euphemistic pre-owned in this contemplate were aggregate one-dimensional retrogression psychoanalysis and possibility examinations of retrogression coefficients that buoy be done, videlicet the F evaluation and the T-test.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \varepsilon$$

Information:

- Y = Short Term Mismatch (STM)
- α = Constant
- X₁ = Capital Asset Ratio (CAR)
- X₂ = Non-Performing Financing (NPF)
- X₃ = Operating Costs Against Operating Income(BOPO)
- X₄ = Financing to Deposito Ratio (FDR)
- X₅ = Third Party Funds (DPK)
- X₆ = Inflation
- X₇ = Bank Indonesia Sharia Certificate (SBIS)

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

CLASSIC ASSUMPTION TEST

Normality Test

A normality evaluation is a evaluation belonging euphemistic pre-owned to evaluation if or not the variables euphemistic pre-owned in a retrogression representation chalk up a conventional distribution. To treasure trove elsewhere if the collections is unremarkably distributed, it buoy be well-tried with The Kolmogorov Smirnov disposition or illustration approach. on the authority of (Singgih Santoso, 2011), The Kolmogorov Smirnov disposition is dual-laned into cardinal categories, much as: distinct possibility expenditure > 0. 05 which have in mind that the collections is a conventional distribution. (2) distinct possibility expenditure < 0. 05 which have in mind that the collections is not unremarkably distributed.

Therein glance at the originators euphemistic pre-owned the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) disposition for the collections normality test. The course of action to ascertain it is to contemplation at the residuary significance value. If the significance is more 0. 05, so residuals are unremarkably apportioned (Duwi Priyatno, 2013). supported on the consequences of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) normality evaluation with personal computer immunodeficiencies victimisationing the SPSS Program. which buoy be seen in tabularise 2 below.

Table 2: Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		60
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	.03866457
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.098
	Positive	.098
	Negative	-.081
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.758
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.614
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source: Study data, processed data

Supported on tabularise 2 in the sky it buoy be recognized that the consequences of statistical psychoanalysis with Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) amounted to 0.098 and significance values (Asymp. 2-tailed) is 0. on account of the expenditure is importantly in a superior way than 0.05, the residuary is unremarkably distributed. This have in mind that $\text{sig} > \alpha$ or $0.614 > 0.05$ have in mind that conventional apportioned residuary collections or retrogression representations accommodate the presumptuousness of normality.

MULTICOLLINEARITY TEST

Multicollinearity examinations are euphemistic pre-owned to evaluation if in retrogression representations thither is a coefficient of expansion between self-governing variables. A first-class retrogression representation should not correlative with self-governing variables. moreover, multicollinearity buoy be seen by comparing broad-mindedness and disagreement ostentatiousness factor (VIF) values. It take place if the broad-mindedness expenditure < 0.10 or $\text{VIF} > 10$. The multicollinearity evaluation consequences buoy be seen in the undermentioned table.

Table 3: Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	X1_CAR	.084	11.945
	X2_NPF	.121	8.271
	X3_BOPO	.108	9.276
	X4_FDR	.136	7.369
	X5_DPK	.034	29.488
	X6_INFLASI	.232	4.309
	X7_SBIS	.365	2.741
a. Dependent Variable: Y_STM			

Source: Study data, processed data

Tabularise 3 in the sky demonstrates that the broad-mindedness values of the automobile and DPK variables euphemistic pre-owned in this evaluation retrogression representation are not to be complimentary from multicollinearity tests, in over-the-counter brief conversation they buoy not be trusted. Where the VIF expenditure for the majuscule assets property correspondence (CAR) changeable of $11,945 > 10$ and broad-mindedness of $0.084 < 0.10$, and the expenditure of thirdly congregation reserve changeable VIF (DPK) of $29,488 > 10$ and broad-mindedness of $0.034 < 0.10$ as a result automobile and DPK variables are alleged

multicollinearity symptoms. in consequence automobile and DPK variables be required to be distant from the model.

Table 3: Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	X2_NPF	.161	6.228
	X3_BOPO	.317	3.151
	X4_FDR	.385	2.598
	X6_INFLASI	.452	2.210
	LN X7_SBIS	.557	1.796
a. Dependent Variable: Y_STM			

Source: Study data,processed data

Supported on the tabularise in the sky as severals automobile and DPK variables are excluded from the model, each variables are complimentary of multicollinearity tests. The multicollinearity examinations for each evaluation changeable are; first off the VIF expenditure for NPF variables is $6,228 < 10$ and broad-mindedness is $0.161 > 0$. in consequence the NPF variables are alleged as no manifestations of multicollinearity. Second, the VIF expenditure for BOPO variables is $3,151 < 10$ and broad-mindedness is $0.317 > 0$. in consequence the BOPO variables are alleged as no manifestations of multicollinearity. Third, the VIF expenditure for the FDR variables is $2,598 < 10$ and the broad-mindedness of $0.385 > 0$. in consequence the FDR variables are alleged as no manifestations of multicollinearity. Fourth, the VIF expenditure for ostentatiousness variables of $2,210 < 10$ and broad-mindedness of $0.452 > 0$. in consequence the ostentatiousness variables are alleged as no manifestations of multicollinearity. Fifth, the VIF expenditure for the SBIS variables is $1,796 < 10$ and the broad-mindedness of $0.557 > 0$. in consequence the SBIS variables are alleged as no manifestations of multicollinearity. From the collections in the sky it buoy be terminated that the retrogression representation is expenditure using.

HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST

Heteroskedasticity examinations are euphemistic pre-owned to evaluation if in retrogression representations thither is disagreement nonconformity from residuary individual examination to another. If the disagreement from residuary individual examination to another examination stays behind it is titled homoscedasticity. If it is at variance it is titled heteroscedasticity. A first-class retrogression representation is a homoskedasticity or individual that does not eventualize heteroskedasticity. The contemplate euphemistic pre-owned elsewhere by

sounding at machination sea-charts to ascertain the non-appearance of heteroskedasticity. The consequences of the Heterosdakticity evaluation buoy be seen in digital audiotape 2 below.

Figure 2: Heteroskedasticity Test

Source: Study data,processed data

Supported on digital audiotape 2 in the sky it is appreciated that the specks on the scatterplot illustration spread out diffuse with unpredictable archetypes and farther down the character 0 on the Y-axis. in this manner it buoy be terminated that thither is no disputed point with heteroskedasticity in the retrogression model.

AUTOCORRELATION TEST

Autocorrelation is the formal propinquity of correlations between colleagues of a exemplification that are classified by time. This presumptuousness abnormality unremarkably put in an appearance on examinations that application time-series data. The aftermath of autocorrelation in a retrogression representation is that the exemplification modification cannot characterize its inhabitant variant. As a result, the resulting retrogression representation cannot be euphemistic pre-owned to approximate the expenditure of drug-addicted variables at the values of trustworthy self-governing variables. The consequences of the Autocorrelation evaluation buoy be seen in tabularise 4 below.

Table4: Autocorrelation Test

Model Summary ^b	
Model	Durbin-Watson
1	.856
a. Predictors: (Constant), LN_ X7_SBIS, X6_INFLASI, X4_FDR, X3_BOPO, X2_NPF	
b. Dependent Variable: Y_STM	

Source: Study data, processed data

To ascertain the formal propinquity of autocorrelation buoy be finished by victimising Durbin Watson. The consequences of the tabularise in the sky established that Durbin Watson's character is 0. The expenditure is between -2 to +2. As a result, it buoy be terminated that therein contemplate thither is no autocorrelation.

MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Aggregate one-dimensional retrogression psychoanalysis is euphemistic pre-owned to influence how all the more consequence self-governing variables chalk up on drug-addicted variables. So the aggregate one-dimensional retrogression evaluation buoy be seen in tabularise 5 below.

Table 5: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	
		B	Std. Error
1	(Constant)	.336	.301
	X2_NPF	3.647	2.379
	X3_BOPO	-.082	.223
	X4_FDR	-1.208	.246
	X6_INFLASI	4.708	1.107
	LN_X7_SBIS	.088	.028
a. Dependent Variable: Y_STM			

Source: Study data, processed data

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \epsilon$$

$$Y = 0,336 + 3.647 - 0.082 - 1.208 + 4.708 + 0.088 + 49,9$$

From the retrogression equalization in the sky it buoy be understood as; first off the never-ending expenditure of 0. 336 this determination state of affairs that if the values of NPF, BOPO, FDR, Inflation, and SBIS are capable 0, so the expenditure of STM is an aggrandizement of 0. 336 units.

Secondment , the NPF changeable has a cocksureness retrogression coefficient expenditure of 3.It points out that if thither is an aggrandizement in NPF of 1%, so the STM testament aggrandizement by 3. 647% presumptuous over-the-counter self-governing variables are advised constant.

Third, the BOPO changeable has a contradiction retrogression coefficient expenditure of -0. This points out that if thither is an aggrandizement in BOPO of 1%, so the STM testament diminution by -0. 082% presumptuous over-the-counter self-governing variables are advised never-ending.

Fourth, the changeable FDR has a contradiction retrogression coefficient expenditure of -1,208. This points out that if thither is an aggrandizement in FDR of 1%, so the STM testament diminution by -1. 208% presumptuous over-the-counter self-governing variables are advised never-ending.

Fifth, The ostentatiousness changeable has a cocksurenness retrogression coefficient expenditure of 4,708. This points out that if thither is an aggrandizement in ostentatiousness of 1%, so the STM testament aggrandizement by 4. 708% presumptuous over-the-counter self-governing variables are advised constant.

The at the end the SBIS changeable has a cocksurenness retrogression coefficient expenditure of 0. This points out that if thither is an aggrandizement in SBIS by 1%, so STM testament aggrandizement by 0. 088 % presumptuous over-the-counter self-governing variables are advised never-ending.

HYPOTHESIS TEST

DETERMINATION COEFFICIENT TEST (R²)

The core group coefficient of steadfastness is to gauge how all the more the self-governing changeable furnishes to the drug-addicted variable. The higher coefficient of steadfastness have in mind the higher qualification of complimentary variables (X) much as NPF, BOPO, FDR, Inflation, and SBIS in explaining the alteration of changeable substitutions drug-addicted variables (Y) videlicet STM.

Table 6: Determination Coefficient Test (R²)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.737 ^a	.544	.501	.04234
a. Predictors: (Constant), LN_ X7_SBIS, X6_INFLASI, X4_FDR, X3_BOPO, X2_NPF				
b. Dependent Variable: Y_STM				

Source: Study data,processed data

Tabularise 6 in the sky showed that thither was a correlation expenditure R straightforward of 0. 501 or 50. The chain reaction of NPF, BOPO, FDR, Inflation, and SBIS variables was 50. patch the outstanding 49. 9% (100% - 50. 1%) was influenced by over-the-counter variables that were not included in the study.

SIMULTANEOUS TEST (F)

The F evaluation is euphemistic pre-owned to established if each the self-governing variables included in the representation chalk up a reefer consequence on the drug-addicted changeable (Ghozali, 2013). The consequences of the F evaluation buoy be recognized by looking the substantial commensurate (sig) and furthermore by comparing the calculable F with the F table, if it lay hold of simultaneously or not. The consequences of the F evaluation buoy be constitute in tabularise 7 below.

Table 7: Simultaneous Test (F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.115	5	.023	12.870	.000 ^b
	Residual	.097	54	.002		
	Total	.212	59			
a. Dependent Variable: Y_STM						
b. Predictors: (Constant), LN_ X7_SBIS, X6_INFLASI, X4_FDR, X3_BOPO, X2_NPF						

Source: Study data,processed data

Supported on tabularise 7 in the sky It buoy be seen that the expenditure of F was calculable at 12,870 with a substantial commensurate expenditure of 0. It is thanks to the substantial expenditure is few than 0. 000 < 0. 05, and the expenditure F reckons > F of the tabularise (12,870 > 3. 11) with the expenditure F of the tabularise df: $\alpha, (k-1), (n-k)$ or 0. 05, (5-1), (59-5) = 3. It buoy be terminated that the variables NPF, BOPO, FDR, Inflation, and SBIS importantly consequence STM.

PARTIAL TEST (T)

This statistical evaluation directs to established until when the consequence of individual changeable NPF, BOPO, FDR, Inflation, and SBIS one at a time (partially) in explaining the alteration of drug-addicted variables (STM) well-tried at the import commensurate be required to be smaller than 0. 05 (Ghozali, 2013). To treasure trove elsewhere the t-test is by comparing the expenditure of t estimate with t tabularise.

Table 8: Partial Test (t)

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
1	(Constant)	.336	.301	1.116	.269
	X2_NPF	3.647	2.379	1.533	.131
	X3_BOPO	-.082	.223	-.366	.716
	X4_FDR	-1.208	.246	-4.910	.000
	X6_INFLASI	4.708	1.107	4.255	.000
	LN_X7_SBIS	.088	.028	3.102	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Y_STM

Source: Study data, processed data

On the authority of the tabularise in the sky it buoy be seen that NPF variables statistically established undistinguished consequences values in a superior way than α ($0.131 > 0.05$) patch the t expenditure of 1.533 and at t tabularise of 1.67065 ($df(n-k) 60-6 = 54$, $\alpha = 0$). in this manner t reckons $<$ t tabularise ($1.533 < 1.67065$) which have in mind that H_a is forsook and H_0 is accepted. As a result, it buoy be terminated that the NPF changeable a certain extent has no substantial chain reaction on the STM.

Hard by The BOPO changeable statistically demonstrates undistinguished consequences at values in a superior way than α ($0.716 > 0.05$), the t expenditure of t reckons -0.366 and at t tabularise is 1.67065 ($df(n-k) 60-6 = 54$, $\alpha = 0$). in this manner t reckons the $<$ t tabularise ($-0.366 < 1.67065$) which have in mind that H_a is forsook and H_0 is accepted. in consequence it buoy be terminated that the BOPO changeable a certain extent has no substantial chain reaction on the STM changeable.

What is more the changeable FDR statistically demonstrates substantial consequences value. It is smaller than α ($0.000 < 0.05$), patch t calculable values of -4,910 and at t comestibles of 1.67065 ($df(n-k) 60-6 = 54$, $\alpha = 0$). in this manner t reckons $>$ t tabularise ($-4.910 > 1.67065$) which have in mind that H_0 is forsook and H_a is accepted. in consequence It buoy be terminated that the changeable FDR a certain extent lay hold of the STM.

Furthermore, ostentatiousness variables statistically established substantial consequences value. It is smaller than α ($0.000 < 0.05$), patch t calculable values of 4,255 and at t comestibles of 1.67065 ($df(n-k) 60-6 = 54$, $\alpha = 0$). in this manner t estimate $>$ t tabularise ($4,255 > 1.67065$) which have in mind that H_0 is forsook and H_a accepted. As a determination it buoy be terminated that ostentatiousness changeable a certain extent lay hold of STM.

The at the end the changeable SBIS statistically demonstrates a substantial determination value. It is smaller than α ($0.003 < 0.05$), patch the t expenditure of t reckons $-4,910$ and at t tabularise of 1.67065 ($df(n-k) 60-6 = 54$, $\alpha = 0$. in this manner t estimate $< t$ tabularise ($-4.910 > 1.67065$) which have in mind that H_0 is forsook and H_a is accepted. as a result it buoy be terminated that the SBIS changeable a certain extent lay hold of the STM.

INTERPRETATION

Supported on the consequences of the contemplate in the sky the consequences of each self-governing changeable on the drug-addicted variables are described as; first off the chain reaction of NPF on STM. The evaluation consequences showed that the NPF changeable did not influence STM. As it has a substantial expenditure of 0.131 in a superior way than 0.05 and a calculable t expenditure of $1.533 < t$ tabularise 1 . as a result it buoy be terminated that The STM correspondence is never-ending although thither is an aggrandizement and diminution in the NPF ratio. The consequences of this contemplate are backed by Nisrina Kamila's evaluation (2018), it is constitute that NPL did not consequence deposit liquidity. It is thanks to the intermediate NPL of commercial-grade botanists sampled is by oneself 2% to 3% and the proportion is all the more farther down the uttermost limitation establish by deposit Indonesia which is 5% . The consequences of this evaluation differentiate with the consequences of evaluation conducted by Nur Suhartatik, and Rohmawati Kusumaningias (2012), Prihatiningsih (2012), Oktaviani alvita kusumawati (2021) which explained NPF variables influenced deposit liquidity.

Second, the chain reaction of BOPO on STM. supported on the evaluation end result it is recognized that the BOPO changeable did not influence the STM. As it has a substantial expenditure of 0.716 in a superior way than 0.05 and the calculable expenditure of $0.366 < t$ tabularise 1 . as a result It buoy be terminated that the STM correspondence is never-ending although thither is an aggrandizement and diminution in the BOPO ratio. The consequences of this contemplate are backed by the evaluation of Ika Puspasari (2017), it is constitute that BOPO did not consequence deposit STM. patch the consequences of this contemplate argue against the consequences of Agustina's contemplate (2013) which explicit that BOPO pretentious liquidity.

Third, the chain reaction of FDR on STM. supported on the evaluation end result it is recognized that the changeable FDR influenced STM. As it had a substantial expenditure of 0.000 which is few than 0.05 and the expenditure of t calculable $-4,910 < t$ tabularise 1 . As a result, it is terminated that the in a superior way correspondence of FDR pretentious by high-pitched funding the higher jeopardy happened. This consideration would chalk up a deficient consequence on the consummation of the bank's short-run obligations.

Fourth, the chain reaction of ostentatiousness on STM. supported on the consequences of the test, it is recognized that the ostentatiousness changeable pressures STM. As it had a substantial expenditure of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 and the expenditure of t calculable $4.255 > t$ tabularise 1 . It buoy be terminated that the higher the ostentatiousness proportion the higher expenditure of artifacts testament increase. As a result, the purchasers

testament discontinue any of their resources in Islamic botanists to satisfy their day-after-day needs. in consequence Islamic botanists be required to aggrandizement their liquidness ratios to achieve their short-run obligations. The consequences of this contemplate were in occupation with the consequences of evaluation conducted by Lina Nugraha aristocrat (2017), Aulia Nazala Ramadhani (2016), Waeibrorheem Waemustafa, Suriani Sukri (2016), Mohamed Aymen Ben Moussa (2015).

Fifth, the chain reaction of SBIS on STM. supported on the evaluation end result it is recognized that the SBIS changeable pressures STM. As it had a substantial expenditure of 0.003 which is smaller than 0.05 and a calculable t expenditure of $3.102 < t$ tabularise 1. The determination of deposit Indonesia is to publication SBIS is to discontinue or abbreviate the proportion of almighty dollar in circulation. deposit Indonesia expectations that by issuing SBIS severals general public testament invest in the SBIS. therein case, it does not eliminate the possibleness that Islamic deposit resources purchasers testament transposition to invest in SBIS issued by deposit Indonesia. in this manner if severals resources purchasers transposition to placing the SBIS, so the liquidness commensurate of Islamic botanists be required to be high-pitched to be accomplished to effectuate their short-run responsibilities much as continuance accomplished to accommodate purchaser be in want of when withdrawing funds. The consequences of this contemplate are in occupation with evaluation conducted by amir Yanuardi (2011) and obstinate to the evaluation conducted by Nur Suhartatik and Rohmawati Kusumaningtias (2013).

CONCLUSION

The consequences of this contemplate showed that automobile and dpk variables did not effectuate the multicollinearity indispensable test, in consequence automobile and dpk variables were excluded from the model. The contemplate terminated that fdr, inflation, and sbis a certain extent influence stm variables. Npf and bopo variables a certain extent do not influence stm variables. Where fdr has the virtually consequence on stm. In consequence islamic banking in indonesia be required to be accomplished to cope the fdr correspondence as efficaciously as accomplishable so that the stm correspondence business agreement to decrease.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adiwarman Karim. (2017). *Ekonomi Makro Islam*. Rajagrafindo Persada.
- Adrian Sutedi. (2012). *Aspek Hukum Pengadaan Barang & Jasa dan Berbagai Permasalahan*. Sinar Grafika.
- Alhamda. (2016). *Buku Ajar Metlit dan Statistik*. CV. Budi Utama.
- Arifin, Z. (2009). *Dasar-Dasar Manajemen Bank Syariah*. Pustaka Alvabet.
- Asfia Murni. (2013). *Ekonomi Makro*. PT Refika Aditama.
- Bank Indonesia. (2012). *Kodifikasi Peraturan Bank Indonesia Kelembagaan Penilaian Tingkat Kesehatan Bank*. Pusat Riset dan Edukasi Bank Sentral.
- Budiman, I. (2021). *Converting Conventional Banks To Sharia Banks In Aceh: An Effort To Maintain A Stable Economy In The Covid-19 Outbreak*. Share: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Islam, 10(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.22373/share.v10i1.8337>

- Dendawijaya, L. (2009). *Manajemen Perbankan*. Ghalia Indonesia.
- Dhika Rahma Dewi. (2010). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Bank Syariah Indonesia. *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 1–36.
- Duwi Priyatno. (2013). *Mandiri Belajar Analisis Data dengan SPSS*. Mediakom.
- Dwi Nur'aini Ihsan. (2015). *Manajemen Treasury Bank Syariah*. UIN Jakarta Press.
- Fahmi, I. (2015). *Analisis Laporan Keuangan*. Alfabeta.
- Ghozali, I. (2013). *Aplikasi Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS*. Undip.
- Gita Danupranata. (2015). *Buku Ajar Manajemen Perbankan Syariah*. Salemba Empat.
- Hasibuan, A. F. H., Fuadi, F., & Syahputra, A. (2021). The Effect Of The Sharia Supervisory Board And The Board Of Commissioners On The Financial Performance Of Sharia Commercial Banks In Indonesia. *At-Tijarah: Jurnal Penelitian Keuangan Dan Perbankan Syariah*. <https://doi.org/10.52490/at-tijarah.v3i1.1273>
- Indo Yama N. dan Hemmy Fauzan. (2006). *Pengantar Bisnis dan Manajemen*. UIN Jakarta Press.
- Kasmir. (2016). *Analisis Laporan Keuangan*. PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Kumaedi, S. R. dan E. M. (2014). Analisis Likuiditas dan Rentabilitas Keuangan Bank Dalam Menilai Kinerja Bank Syariah Mandiri (Studi Kasus Pada PT Bank Syariah Mandiri Tahun 2003-2009). *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Riset Akuntansi*, 11(2).
- Matnin. (2016). Kinerja Dan Kesehatan Bank Islam. *DINAR: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 1(1).
- Monika, A., Azam, A. N., & Teguh, S. I. (2021). The Impact of Fintech Development to Profitability of Islamic Bank. *International Journal of Research and Review*.
- Nur Mawaddah. (2015). Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Profitabilitas Bank Syariah. *Jurnal Etikonomi*, 14(2), 241–256.
- Purwanto, P. (2021). Non Performing Financing And Efficiency Of Islamic Banks In Indonesia. *Journal of Business Studies and Mangement Review*. <https://doi.org/10.22437/jbsmr.v4i2.13289>
- Sentosa Sembiring. (2006). *Himpunan Lengkap Undang-Undang tentang Perbankan*. Nuansa Aulia.
- Sihabuddin Enden, W. (2021). Pembiayaan Mudharabah dan Pembiayaan Musyarakah Terhadap Tingkat Profitabilitas (ROE) Bank Umum Syariah. *Maro Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah San Bisnis*, 4(1), 8–18.
- Singgih Santoso. (2011). *Buku Latihan SPSS Statistik Parametrik*. PT. Elex.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. In Ke-26.
- Suhardjono. (2011). *Manajemen Perbankan*. BPFE.
- Tony wijaya. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Ekonomi: Teori dan Praktek*. Graha Ilmu.
- Widajatun, V. W., & Ichسانی, S. (2019). The Impact of Credit, Liquidity, Operational and Market Risks on Return on Asset. *Global Business and Management Research*.